

JAVASCRIPT O'ZGARUVCHILAR

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Qo'qon DPI, "Matematika-informatika" yo'nalishi

3- bosqich talabasi

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu tezisda JavaScriptda o'zgaruvchilar haqida qisqacha ma'lumot berilgan.

Tayanch so'zlar: JavaScript, o'zgaruvchilar, var, let, const.

JavaScript dasturlash tilida o'zgaruvchilarni e'lon qilishning 4 xil usuli bor bo'lib quyidagilar kiradi.

var

let

const

hech narsa ishlatmasdan

O'zgaruvchilar nima?

O'zgaruvchilar - bu ma'lumotlarni saqlash uchun konteynerlar (ma'lumotlar qiymatlarini saqlash). Ushbu misolda, **x**, **y** va **z**, o'zgaruvchilar bo'lib, ular **var** kalit so'z bilan e'lon qilinadi:

```
var x = 5;
var y = 6;
var z = x + y;
```

Ushbu misolni **let** kalit so'zi bilan e'lon qilishga misol keltiramiz.

```
let x = 5;
let y = 6;
let z = x + y;
```

Ushbu misolda, **x**, **y** va **z**, e'lon qilinmagan o'zgaruvchilar:

```
x = 5;
y = 6;
z = x + y;
```

JavaScript da **const** ni qachon foydalanish kerak?

Kod yozish jarayonida umumiy qoida bo'lishini hohlasangiz ushbu holatda siz **const** kalit so'zi bilan o'zgaruvchini e'lon qilsangiz bo'ladi. Bunda o'zgaruvchini o'zgartirib bo'lmaydi. Misol uchun PI ni qiymati o'zgarmas bo'lib uni const bilan e'lon qilishimiz mumkin.

```
const PI = 3.14;
```

JavaScript da **var** ni qachon ishlatish kerak?

Har doim JavaScript o'zgaruvchilarini **var** va **let** yoki **const** bilan e'lon qiling. **var** kalit so'zi 1995 yildan 2015 yilgacha barcha JavaScript kodlarida qo'llaniladi. **let**

kalit so'zi 2015 yildan boshlab JavaScript kodlarida qo'llaniladi. Agar siz eski browser ishlatsangiz u holda **var** kalit so'zidan foydalanishingiz zarur bo'ladi.

Foydalanilgan saytlar ro'yxati:

1. <https://uzbekdevs.uz/darsliklar/javascript/javascript-da-o-zgaruvchilar> - Javascript o'zgaruvchilari haqidagi malumotlar shundan olindi.
2. Juraev, Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich. "Prospects for the development of professional training of students of professional educational institutions using electronic educational resources in the environment of digital transformation." *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research* 3.10 (2022): 158-162.
3. Juraev, Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich. "The value of open mass competitions in the process of digitalization of extracurricular activities of schoolchildren." *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal* 3.10 (2022): 338-344.
4. Jo'rayev, Muzaffarjon. "Professional ta'lim jarayonida fanlararo uzvilik va uzliksizlikni ta'minlash o'quvchilari kasbiy tayyorgarligining muhim omili sifatida." *Zamonaviy dunyoda amaliy fanlar: Muammolar va yechimlar* 1.29 (2022): 43-46.
5. Juraev, M. M. "OA Qo'ysinov Description of the methodological basis for ensuring interdisciplinary continuity of the subject "Computer Science and Information Technology" in vocational education." *JournalNX-A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed* 7.10 (2021).
6. Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon. "Description of the Methodological Basis for Ensuring Interdisciplinary Continuity of the Subject" *Computer Science and Information TECHNOLOGY in Vocational Education.* *JournalNX* 7.10: 223-225.
7. Khasanov, A. R. (2022). LEARNING IS A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH AS A CONTENT UPDATE STEP. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(12), 217-223.
8. Khasanov, A. R. (2022). Development of information competence of future informatics teachers as a pedagogical problem. *Open Access Repository*, 9(12), 73-79.
9. Xasanov, A. R. (2021, May). USE OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES AND INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING COMPUTER SCIENCE. In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 198-199).
10. Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon. "CURRENT STATUS OF THE SCIENCE OF INFORMATICS AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION SYSTEM, EXISTING PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS, PRINCIPLES AND CONTENT OF THE SCIENCE ORGANIZATION." *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal* 10.12 (2022): 327-331.
11. Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon. "Professional Educational Institutions Theoretical and Practical Basis of Development of the Content of Pedagogical Activity of Teachers of" *Information and Information Technologies*." *Open Access Repository* 9.12 (2022): 85-89.
12. Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon. "Experience Of Cambridge Curricula In Ensuring The Continuity Of Curricula In The Field Of "Computer Science And Information Technology" In The System Of Professional Education." *The American Journal of Interdisciplinary Innovations and Research* 3.11 (2021): 26-32.
13. Juraev, Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich. "Theoretical and practical principles of improving the content of the pedagogical activity of ICT teachers of professional educational institutions in the conditions of information of education." (2022).

- 14.Juraev, Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich. "Methodological foundations for improving the content of training future ict teachers in the conditions of digital transformation of education." (2022): 9-11.
- 15.Melikyzievich, Siddikov Ilkhom, et al. "THE METHOD OF REFERENCE TESTS FOR THE DIAGNOSIS OF DIGITAL DEVICES." International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education 14.7 (2022).
- 16.Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon. "Designing an electronic didactic environment to ensure interdisciplinary integration in the teaching of" Informatics and information technologies" during professional education." Confrencea 11.11 (2023): 78-82.
- 17.Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon, and Aroyev Dilshod Davronovich. "INTERDISCIPLINARY INTEGRATION IS AN IMPORTANT PART OF DEVELOPING THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF STUDENTS." Open Access Repository 9.1 (2023): 93-101.
- 18.Juraev, M. M. "ZY Xudoyberdiyev Theoretical analysis of the continuity model of computer science and information technology in the System of professional education." European Scholar Journal (ESJ)//ISSN (E): 2660-5562.
- 19.Xudayberdiyev, Zayniddin Yavkachevich, and Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich Juraev. "Theoretical analysis of the continuity model of computer science and information technology in the system of professional education." (2021).